

A Review of the Literature on the Role of Social Capital in Tourism Growth

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ABSTRACT: To improve people's welfare, economic growth has always focused on the development of the secondary sector. The secondary sector, on the other hand, has not fully provided for the community's needs. This is due to the community's current social capital being underutilized. One of the main drivers of tourism development is social capital. Social capital is a driving force at various stages and is regarded as an important mechanism in the success of tourism planning and development. It can also be used to encourage tourism development in urban areas in order to create sustainable tourism. Social capital is the capacity to understand how a community builds, understands, and participates in tourism growth. Communities with high social capital can present better conditions for tourism growth, and community development focus on tourism can be an important element in the regional economy's continuity and growth. The development of social capital studies in tourism growth should be visualized for a more subjective analysis. In order to collect data in this study, PoP software was in use. The existing database is then processed with the VOS Viewer software. This software collects and analyzes all of the keywords in the abstract one by one. VOS Viewer identified some of the most frequently discussed keywords in 53 journals related to social capital in tourism, including tourism, tourism development, relationship, and social capital.

KEYWORDS: Social Capital, Tourism, Bibliometric

I. INTRODUCTION

To improve people's welfare, economic growth has historically focused on the development of the secondary sector. The secondary sector, on the other hand, has not fully provided for the community's welfare. This is due to the fact that the community's existing social capital is still underutilized (Putri et al., 2019). Social capital is widely acknowledged as a complex influence that helps society in achieving its desired level of economic growth. Social capital is a productive resource that can boost economic growth and welfare, and it is influenced by social capital elements (Daskalopoulou, 2020). Individually owned social capital is used not only for the benefit of individuals and communities, but it is also very important for the economy on a macro level. Social capital, particularly bridging capital, has the potential to boost job creation. People who have strong connections and relationships can have faster economic growth than those who do not. So that a society with a lot of social capital can build and maintain a lot of per capita income (Engbers & Rubin, 2018).

Social capital is a valuable resource that can be factored into the economic growth equation. Social capital can also play an important role in economic growth. This is because, through networks and ties, social capital not only unites society, but also unites components in economic growth. All forms of social capital are needed in society to support all forms of collective action, which is expected to continue soon. In the long run, it will become a benchmark for economic growth (Zmyslony et al., 2020). There are two very influential components in social capital by definition. First, it requires the existence of a relationship, which can be formal, such as at work, or informal, such as friendship. Second, social capital can generate personal or social value. Other types of capital, such as financial, physical, or human capital, are similar to social capital in that they are focused on capital with elements of social relations. Social capital is also viewed as a resource that is used in economic processes (Engbers & Rubin, 2018).

In economic activities, social capital can also help to reduce or eliminate transaction costs, resulting in increased efficiency. People who are concerned about various aspects and dimensions of life activities, people who pay attention to and trust one another, can foster a peaceful, friendly, and tranquil social life (Syahyuti, 2008). Communities with a high social capital are thought to be able to solve complex problems more easily.

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Tourism is one of the important sectors that can help a community's economic progress both locally and globally. Tourism has a major role in national and regional economic growth, particularly in terms of increasing foreign exchange and income (Sokhanvar, 2019). Government revenue and the balance of payments have increased both directly and indirectly as a result of the rapid growth of tourism, which has resulted in increased household income (Khalil & Kakar, 2015). Not only that, but tourism can create jobs, stimulate the tourism industry's growth, and trigger overall economic growth (Lee & Chang, 2008). To increase tourism resources, it is critical to use social capital as a driving force for growth in the tourism industry. One of them is a social networking website. Individuals can use networks to generate strong social capital because networks are a strategic dimension of social capital (Jóhannesson et al., 2003). Relationships in social capital can last a long time when networks are built with a strong bond.

Trust in social capital is regarded as a significant indicator that can act as a catalyst for societal development (Strzelecka & Okulicz-Kozaryn, 2018). Trust in the community can also be used to build an institution that is in line with the social capital structure and to strengthen community groups' networks. As a result, the role of social capital in society, particularly in tourism growth, must be considered in the development of the tourism industry. Because social capital is the most basic capital that a community must-own for all economic development activities to achieve its objectives. By examining the function of social capital in tourism growth, it is expected to be able to develop human and natural resources, as well as increase the economy and create jobs, resulting in the realization of sustainable tourism growth.

II. METHODS

This research employs bibliometric methods to identify, assess, and interpret all available research to provide answers to research questions. This method involves the researcher summarizing and analyzing relevant literature before engaging in a discussion. A systematic method is used to conduct the literature review, as well as mind mapping that emphasizes knowledge using the bibliometric method. Bibliometric reviews are common in scientific disciplines and focus on qualitative analyses of journal papers, books, and other forms of written communication (Heersmink et al, 2010).

Identify appropriate search terms

Social capital, Tourism, and Social capital in tourism were among the keywords used in the search and data collection. To increase the likelihood of finding highly relevant articles, you must first choose the most appropriate search terms. For the most comprehensive coverage of the literature, a broad perspective is required. Google Scholar, Library Genesis, and Publish or Perish are the digital-based search engines used, and they are used to search by title and keywords.

Table 1. Initial Search Results

Search Keywords	Search results
Social Capital	2.620.000
Tourism	3.080.000
Social capital in Tourism	123
Total	5.700.123

(Source: google scholar)

A. Initial search results

We used title and keyword searches in the Google Scholar database during the initial data search. By gathering and archiving journals that contain these predefined search terms. Thousands of journals were found during the initial search. We did not specify a period for this initial search, so it includes a large number of writings that are irrelevant to this study.

B. Refinement of search results

We issue articles that do not meet our screening criteria at this stage, and we make a 5-year range from 2017 to 2021. The inclusion and exclusion criteria were used to select the literature (Wahono, 2015). Studies without strong validation or included in experimental results, as well as studies that do not discuss social capital, tourism, economic growth, or those related to these keywords, are examples of dataset exceptions. Studies in the field of social capital, tourism, economic growth are included in the dataset used. To make data compilation easier, we use the application publish or perish to select all existing data sets.

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Table 2. Refinement of Search Results

Search Keywords	Search results
Social Capital	940
Tourism	920
Social capital in Tourism	51
Total	1921

(Source: google scholar, 2017-2021)

C. Compile the initial statistical data

The search is generated using the software publish or perish and then exported to RIS format, which includes all relevant information about the journal, such as the title, author's name, abstract, keywords, and journal specifications. The data was analyzed so that, between 2017 and 2021, 1921 journal articles could be published or perish obtained using the data search matrix below.

Table 3. Data Search Matrix

Matrik Data	Social capital	Tourism	Social Capital in Tourism
Source	Google Scholar	Google Scholar	Google Scholar
Papers	940	920	61
Citations	14150	37894	1170
Cites/year	3537.50	9473.50	68.82
Cites/paper	15.05	41.19	19.18
Author/papa	2.90	2.73	2.16
h-index	49	83	15
g-index	83	124	34
hl,norm	27	50	13
hl,annual	6.75	12.50	0.76
hA-index	27	44	9

(Source: Publish or perish)

D. Data analysis

A bibliometric analysis of databases collected from publish or perish is presented in this study. This study examines the pattern of citation networks and the relevant journal literature to see how the concept of social capital has been applied in the tourism sector. The citation network analysis allows for the identification of journal literature that is critical to the introduction of new concepts in academia. A two-stage search for relevant literature was conducted. To begin, search Google Scholar for all articles containing the keywords social capital, tourism, and social capital in tourism. We found a variety of articles in this first search, including some from previous years. We only chose studies from the first search that covered the years 2017 to 2021. So, in phase two, we conduct another search. We used the software publish or perish in the second stage of the search to make the search and data collection easier. So that we can compile a database that is relevant to this study. The collected database is then saved in RIS format for further processing with the software of choice.

Several researchers have created software to visualize journal literature networks based on bibliometric data. VOSViewer, Science to Science, BibExcel, CoPalRed, Network Workbench, VantagePoint, and CiteSpace are some of the programs used. This study employs the software VOSViewer to view the journal literature network, which was chosen from a variety of options. VOSViewer can be used to create data maps based on keywords in the database and to view bibliometric maps of authors and journals based on the database that has been collected. This software displays bibliometric mapping in three different visualizations: network, overlay, and density. VOSViewer also can group keywords into different clusters.

III. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

A. Social Capital

The basic principle of social capital is a set of social and cultural values that recognize the importance of cooperation owned by community groups, which can enable these community groups to progress and develop with their own strengths. So that, to

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achieve economic development success, social capital can be used to increase community empowerment, because outside assistance is insufficient to overcome the economic difficulties faced; instead, they must work together to find the best way to overcome these problems using the potential they have (Syahra, 2003). Lyda Judson Hanifan was the first to introduce the concept of social capital. In his writings, he reveals that social capital is not a capital in the sense of wealth in the form of money, but rather a real capital that plays an important role in social life. Goodwill, a sense of friendship, mutual sympathy, as well as social relations and close cooperation between individuals and families that make up a social group, are all included. The evolution of social capital studies should be visualized for more subjective analysis. From 2017 to 2021, a total of 995 documents related to social capital were used as a database in this study. The existing database was then processed using the VOSviewer software.

The focus of the analysis is on the distribution of the most common titles and keywords. The goal is to look at some of the most important research topics in social capital. This software collects and analyzes all of the keywords in the abstract one by one. VOS Viewer identified some of the most discussed keywords after analyzing 995 journals related to social capital. VOS Viewer organizes keywords into clusters. The clusters are color-coded for easy identification. The diagram depicts the 43 most common keywords found in social capital research. Nodes with the same color belong to the same cluster. In social capital research, the software identified six clusters. With 12 keywords, the red cluster has the most keywords, led by the keyword social capital. The second cluster, led by the keyword relationship, is green and contains eight keywords. The blue cluster, led by the keyword network, is the third cluster, with a total of seven cluster members. The components of social capital, such as trust and relationships, are described in the third cluster. The yellow cluster, which has six members and is led by Link, is the fourth cluster. Human capital leads the purple cluster, which is the sixth cluster. Finally, the keyword interaction leads to a light blue cluster of five members.

Figure 1. Network Visualization Social Capital

(Source: Processed data with Vosviewer)

B. Tourism Growth

Year after year, tourism is establishing itself as a thriving industry. This is aided by the rapid advancement of information technology, which has accelerated the dynamics of globalization, including the growth of entertainment, recreation, and tourism. Since the end of World War II, international tourism has grown at a rapid pace. Increased urbanization, population, education, and leisure time all increase people's desire to travel in developed countries (tourism). Increases in these components result in increased income and lower international travel costs, contributing significantly to the expansion of tourism (Crouch, 1995). To understand how social capital influences tourism, we must first examine tourism's objects and

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elements. The community involved in tourism activities is the formal object of tourism science. While the elements of tourism include tourist movement, community activities that facilitate tourist movement, and the implications of tourist movement and community activities that facilitate it.

Figure 2. Network Visualization Tourism Growth

(Source: Processed data with Vosviewer)

The evolution of tourism growth studies must be visualized for more subjective analysis. From 2017 to 2021, a total of 995 documents related to tourism growth were used as a database in this research. The existing database was then processed using the VOSViewer software. The analysis focuses on the distribution of the most frequently occurring titles and keywords. The aim is to examine important research topics in the field of social capital. This software collects all the keywords in the abstract to be analyzed one by one. After analyzes 995 journals related to social capital, VOS Viewer came up with some of the most talked-about keywords.

VOS Viewer organizes keywords into clusters. The clusters are color-coded for easy identification. The graph depicts the 51 most common keywords in the field of research tourism growth. The nodes with the same color belong to the same cluster. In total, the software identifies six clusters in the growth of research tourism. With 14 keywords, the red cluster has the most keywords, led by the keyword tourism growth. The second cluster, led by keyword development, is green, with 11 keywords. The blue cluster, which contains nine keywords and is led by the keyword tourism, is the third cluster. The yellow cluster, which has seven members and is led by the keyword economic growth, is the fourth cluster. The purple cluster, which is led by the keyword tourism industry, is the seventh cluster. Finally, a three-member light blue cluster led by the keyword country.

C. Social Capital in Tourism Growth

Capital is that part of the value that capitalists see as the thing that can control the means of production in the circulation of commodities and money in the production and consumption process, and is also seen as part of the surplus value of a production process (Marx & Engels, 1978). Human capital is viewed as a long-term investment with a predictable return (Jóhannesson et al. 2003). Individuals engaged in interactions and networks profit from social capital, which is a type of neo-capital theory. Social capital, according to this journal, is defined as a resource embedded in social structures that are accessed and mobilized for a specific purpose. This social resource (social capital) explains how having access to and using social resources can improve one's socioeconomic status (Lin, 2005).

Social capital is a tool for increasing economic output that works in the same way as human capital, allowing it to provide social goods through participation in the social sector (Hassan & Birungi, 2003) (Antoci et al., 2009). By enabling information sharing, reducing opportunistic behavior, and facilitating collective decision-making, social capital contributes to economic, social, and political development (Jones & Woolcock, 2007). Social capital is derived from social relationships that are based on

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social networks, norms, and trust, and it also has the potential to create long-lasting institutional networks (Hauberer, 2010). Social capital has a significant impact on the growth and development of various economic sectors. Shows the findings of studies conducted in various countries that show that strong social capital will stimulate the growth of various economic sectors due to a high level of trust and closeness of relationships among economic actors in a widening network, including in the tourism sector (Fukuyama, 2012).

Social capital is one of the driving forces behind the growth of the tourism industry. Social capital is a driver at various stages and is regarded as an important mechanism in the success of tourism planning and development. It can also be used to encourage tourism development in urban areas to achieve sustainable tourism (Yudha et al., 2019). Social capital has emerged significantly as the main mechanism that encourages and attracts people to participate in the area in tourism development, giving rise to participation from local residents who have a strong sense of and mutual respect for one another (Pongponrat & Chantradoan, 2012).

Institutions that are following the structure of social capital can be created using social capital in the form of trust in society (Jóhannesson et al., 2003). Because it can strengthen the relationship of one community involved in the tourism industry with other communities or tourists who come, trust in groups with strong ties to the tourism sector has a big impact on tourism growth. Not only that, but public trust in government and politics can influence tourism growth strategy; so, the tourism sector should be considered as a means of supporting regional economic growth (Nunkoo & Smith, 2014). Social capital can also form a network through trust in society, which can create institutions that are in line with the social capital structure, resulting in a strong network. The existence of a network allows for the emergence of new ideas that can help tourism grow faster. The type and nature of the network have a significant impact on the development of tourism innovation. Because this can underpin the formation and management of strong network alliances, innovative tourism companies must be consciously and actively involved in the formation of external networks and internal cooperation (Petrou & Daskalopoulou, 2013).

The development of innovation in the tourism sector can be aided by relationships and networks. The effect will vanish if the strength of the relationship is too close and excessive. This is due to the formation of a structure indicating information and knowledge transfer that does not occur in all clusters and is only limited to organizations that form a specific relationship (Garca-Villaverde & Martnez-Pérez, 2018). Due to the limited rewards provided by the environment, social capital values may be threatened and eroded. This is because the social capital values (trust, mutual respect, personal bonds, shared values) that are created within the group/community are regarded as a valuable legacy that can help the community maintain institutional integrity, which is highly valued and neglected by some members of the community (Williams & Elkhashab, 2018)

Social capital is the ability to comprehend how a community constructs, comprehends and participates in tourism development. Communities with high social capital can present better conditions for tourism development, and community development that focuses on tourism can be an important element in the regional economy's continuity and growth (Fernandes, 2011). People's lack of understanding of tourism, on the other hand, is a barrier to tourism development, particularly in rural areas (Fernandes, 2011) (Claiborne, 2010). Community participation in formal tourism institutions, on the other hand, is still very low, because decision-making does not involve the local community, and many people are unaware of the importance of tourism development. As a result of these two factors, tourism growth is slowed (Okazaki, 2008). As a result, social capital must be utilized more effectively to have a more tangible impact on tourism and economic growth. And all aspects of social capital, particularly trust, bonds, networks, and values, should be modified to increase development potential. travel and tourism (Nordin & Westlund, 2009).

The evolution of social capital studies in tourism growth should be visualized for more subjective analysis. We couldn't find journals that used the keyword social capital in tourism growth using the software we use to collect data, namely PoP, so we used the keyword social capital in tourism instead. From 2017 to 2021, a total of 53 documents related to social capital in tourism were used as a database in this study. The existing database was then processed using the VOSViewer software. The focus of the study is on the distribution of the most commonly used titles and keywords. The goal is to look at some of the most important research topics in social capital. This software collects and analyzes all of the keywords in the abstract one by one. VOS Viewer generated some of the most talked-about keywords after analyzing 53 journals related to social capital.

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Figure 3. Network Visualization Social Capital In Tourism

(Source: Processed data with Vosviewer)

The goal is to look at some of the most important research topics in social capital. This software collects and analyzes all of the keywords in the abstract one by one. VOS Viewer generated some of the most talked-about keywords after analyzing 53 journals related to social capital. With six keywords, the red cluster has the most keywords, led by the keyword tourism. The second cluster is green, with five keywords, with tourism development leading the way. The blue cluster, which has a total of five keywords and is led by keyword relationship, is the third cluster. The yellow cluster, which has three members and is led by social capital, is the fourth cluster.

IV. CONCLUSION

The productivity of community groups is determined by social capital, which is a horizontal relationship made up of networks governed by norms. This gives rise to the basic concept of social capital, which states that there is a network of norms that support one another in achieving successful economic growth for those who are part of it. Increased urbanization, population, education, and leisure time all increase people's desire to travel in developed countries (tourism). Increases in these components result in increased income and lower international travel costs, contributing significantly to the expansion of tourism. People who participate in tourism activities are referred to as tourism objects. The tourism industry's output includes attractions, transportation, facilities, and institutions. To have a more tangible impact on tourism and economic growth, social capital must be used more specifically.

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